

COMPARISON OF SUTURE RECEIVER TOOL AND CLASSICAL SUTURE RECEIVERS

Ethem Bilgiç^{*,1}, Ali Doğan Bozdağ^{**}, Şükrü Boylu^{**}, Aykut Soyder^{**}, Tülin Boylu^{**}, Eyüp Murat Yılmaz^{**} and Berke Manoğlu^{***}

^{*}Izmir Bozyaka Training and Research Hospital., ^{**}Aydın Adnan Menderes University Hospital., ^{***}Denizli State Hospital.

ABSTRACT Introduction: Wound healing became the primary field of occupation for researchers. Some inflammatory cases occur not only during stitching, but also in course of suture receiving. We designed a new device that is both easy to implement and promotes suture receiving without harming the wound site; and took out a patent for it. We tried to prove the functionality of our new suture receiver device through an animal experiment. **Material Method:** 14 Sprague-Dawley type rats were included in the study in total. They were classified as two groups. The sutures of 7 rats in the first group were received by the new design suture receiver device, while the sutures of 7 rats in the second group were received by forceps and lancet, which is the classic method. The preparation of experimental animals, wounding and wound care technique, the weights of rats, suture receiving rates and wound site histopathologies were evaluated statistically. **Findings:** A significant difference was not found with regards to weights of rats ($p=0,652$). The statistical difference between the new device and the classic method was not significant when suture receiving times were examined ($p<0.05$). When the damages created in tissues as the sutures are received by these two methods are evaluated microscopically, it was determined that any tissue damage was not occurred in both techniques ($p=1,000$). And a significant difference was not seen for both techniques, when the damages they created in tissues were compared microscopically. **Result:** In our study, it became possible to compare a new device and the traditional method and devices that are used for hundreds of years. When viewed from this aspect, it is important with regards to leading similar studies. Using the new device not only provide advantage with regards to both time and performance, but also formed an impression that it will be easier to receive troublesome sutures. The speedup observed as we keep using the new device encourages us for the device to come into practical use.

KEYWORDS suture removal, wound healing, new surgical tool

Introduction

Wound healing has been a major area of interest for researchers for many years. Regardless of the suture material and technique,

it has been revealed that various inflammatory events due to the foreign body reaction will be minimized by the convergence of tissues. At the end of surgery, skin incision is closed with sutures. For suturing, non-absorbable materials such as silk, polypropylene are often used, and these sutures must be removed after the wound has been healed. When taking sutures, especially when receiving the stitches embedded in the tissue, there are risks such as the patient feeling pain, traumatizing the wound that has healed, or even bleeding. If the scissors are to be used in such a wound, the necessity to remove the stitch to be removed should also be able to traumatize the wound. If the scalpel is to be used, there is a possibility of damaging both the wound and the stitcher. In addition, both sides of the ropes entering and exiting the skin can be cut. If this happens, it is very difficult to

Copyright © 2019 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons

DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.suture-receiver-devices-study

First Received: December 26, 2018

Accepted: January 31, 2019

Manuscript Associate Editor: Ivon Ribarova (BG)

¹Izmir Bozyaka Training and Research Hospital; E-mail: blakened_22@yahoo.com

Mobile: +90 5336279774

Fig.1. Scissors and penset from materials used to get sutures by classical method.

remove the part of the suture under the skin, and sometimes it cannot be removed. This piece of yarn cannot be removed, it can form a foreign body reaction, it may be infected. These problems can be eliminated with a better designed tool. In classic method, it is usually used with a collet, a scalpel or a scissor when taking a suture (figure 1).

It will be possible to buy stitches using one hand and one tool with suture receiver. With this tool, it is aimed to speed up the operations and to make the necessary operation easier and faster with a tool and a hand. The new tool tip is in the form of a crimped collet and a triangular blade located a few millimeters away from the curved lower end (figure 2).

With the upper part of the collar closing the sharp side of the blade, there is no risk of knife damaging the wound or injuring the person receiving the stitch. The curved ends of the collar can hold the seam when it is joined, and it is safe to cover the blade (figure 3a,b).

The lower end of the collar passes under the seam and the seam is raised. When the collar is moved a little further, the seam becomes cut (figure 4a,b).

In this way, one edge of the seam is raised by the bent end which is inserted under the seam, and by pushing the forceps forward, it cuts the knife sewing rope next to the curved end (figure 5a,b).

The cutting rope is removed by pulling it with the tip of the forceps (figure 6a,b).

Advantages of the new tool:

- Entering the bottom of the suture, cutting and removal can be done quickly and safely using one hand.
- Even if the suture is embedded in the wound, it can be cut under the stitch thanks to its curved end.
- Since the top of the knife is protected by forceps, it does not harm the patient or the health worker taking the suture.

Nowadays, there is no patented product bearing the characteristics of this design. Similar patents are available, for example,

Fig.2. Suture receiver tool.

and to compare with the suture receiving device:

A.

In international patent document WO2007134214, suture receiving device is mentioned (1) (figure 7). This tool has a cutting section in front of the forceps that extends to the front. The present invention is similar to the invention entitled "Suture Receiver Tool" for fast cutting under the stitching and then pulling and pull-out operations with one hand. However, the suture receiver tool differs from the method of administration and is more advanced.

B.

In United States patent document US35416845, a medical device for cutting and removing stitches is mentioned (2) (figure 8). The present invention consists of a V-shaped cutting tool and a pliers-like tool. The present invention is similar to the invention entitled "Suture Receiver Tool" for fast cutting under the stitching and then pulling and pull-out operations with one hand. However, the suture receiver tool differs from the method of administration and is more advanced.

C.

In United States patent document US4669470, a medical device for cutting and removing stitches is mentioned (3) (figure 9). The present invention comprises a penset-like tool and a cutting element which is in the form of a scissor in the vertical direction to the arms of the forceps. These cutting elements are inwardly inward and are present in both arms. The present invention is similar to the invention entitled "Suture Receiver Tool" for fast cutting under the stitching and then pulling and pull-out operations with one hand. However, the suture receiver tool differs from the method of administration and is more advanced.

When looking at all these devices, the suture receiver tool is thought to be easier to use and more practical.

Fig.3.A. Views of the suture receiver tool from different directions. A: side view.

Fig.3.B. Close-up view of curved nib and blade.

Fig.4.A. Curved tip under sewing. A: Live tissue

Fig.4.B. Curved tip under sewing. B: Model.

Fig.5.A. The blade located behind the bend is cutting the suture.
A: Live tissue

Fig.6.A. After the suture is cut, it is removed by holding it with the ends of the forceps. A: Live tissue

Fig.5.B. The blade located behind the bend is cutting the suture.
B: Model.

Fig.6.B. After the suture is cut, it is removed by holding it with the ends of the forceps. B: Model.

Fig.7. A drawing of International Patent Document WO2007134214.

Fig.8. A drawing of United States patent document US35416845.

Fig.9. A drawing of United States patent document US4669470.

Material And Methods

A total of 14 Sprague-Dawley rats were included in the study. Two groups with seven rats were formed in each group. Rats were determined by random selection. Weight measurement of rats and recorded. The rats were divided into 2 groups by a full-thickness skin incision, and the sutures of 7 rats in the first group were taken with a new design suture receiving device while the sutures of the 7 rats in the second group were taken with the conventional method of penset and scalpel. Ethics committee approval was obtained for the study. The study was carried out in Adnan Menderes University Faculty of Medicine Experimental Animals Unit and Adnan Menderes University Faculty of Medicine Department of Histology and Embryology.

Anesthesia of the rats was provided with 50 mg/kg ketamine hydrochloride and 10 mg/kg xylazine hydrochloride. Rats were placed in the supine position under the heater lamp. Abdomen was shaved and local area cleaning was performed with polyvidone iodine. After the sutures were removed, the wound site was totally excised and placed into containers containing formol and the vessels were numbered for histopathological examination.

A 5 cm incision was made in the middle line extending to the superior of the Xiphoid process with 2 cm superior of the proximal border of the penis (figure 10).

Skin and subcutaneous tissues were incised. Muscle fascia was left intact on the ground. Atraumatic sharp needle 3.0 polypropylene material was incised one by one with 5 cm stitches per suture (figure 11).

2 mg / ml paracetamol was added to drinking water for postoperative pain treatment. Animals were fed in standard boxes for 7 days; daily, general status, body weight, malnutrition, signs of infection and body temperature were evaluated. After seven days, the sutures of the rats in the first group were taken with the suture receiving device (Figure 12), and the sutures of the rats in the second group were taken with the classical method (Figure 13) and the suturing times were recorded. The incision

Fig.10. Incision.

Fig.11. Incision sutured.

Fig.12. Receiving stitches with a new suture receiving tool.

site was then excised for histopathological evaluation and placed in numbered boxes. Stitch times were recorded for statistical comparison. Tissues placed in the numbered boxes with which the technique was obtained were stored for histopathological evaluation.

Changes in the structure of the skin and subcutaneous layers of the samples were investigated. The epidermis basal stratum basal and stratum granulosum, coratum layer consisting of keratinized cells, hair follicles in the dermis layer, epidermal structures with blood and sweat glands and blood vessels were examined. Capillary damage and hemorrhage were noted in both groups. After the sutures were removed, the total excision of the skin and subcutaneous tissue covering the area was evaluated macroscopically by the histopathologist and graded according to the following criteria.

- Ideally taken: 0
- Not ideal: 1

Whether the excised tissue was microscopically traumatized was also graded according to the underlying criteria.

- Normal histopathological examination: 1
- Less damage to tissue: 2
- Moderate damage to tissue: 3
- Severe damage to tissue: 4

Statistical Methods

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program was used to analyze the data. For the analysis of quantitative data, the normal distribution was investigated by Shapiro-Wilk test. In the analysis of variables with normal distribution, parametric methods and nonparametric methods were used in the analysis of variables that did not show normal distribution. Independent t test was used for the comparison of 2 independent groups. The Man Whitney U test was used with non-parametric methods in conjunction with the results of the Monte Carlo simulation

Fig.13. The classical method.

technique. Pearson Chi-square Test (Exact) was used to compare categorical data.

Results

The mean weight of the first group of rats was 292 (280-312) g and the mean weight of the rats in the second group was 289 g (272-305). No statistically significant difference was found between the two groups ($p = 0,652$). When the time of suture removal was examined, the mean time with the new device was 83.57 ± 53.84 seconds and the mean time with the conventional method was 46.43 ± 15.7 seconds. The difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0,123$). In the first group, the first rats had a suture duration of 133 seconds, while the seventh rat had a 33-second period. Therefore, it was observed that the duration of the suture removal was reduced with the new technique between the first and seventh rats. When the sutures were removed from the microscopic examination of the tissue in two techniques, there was no significant tissue damage in both techniques. No significant difference was found between the two techniques in terms of macroscopic damage in tissue. In the histopathological examination of the skin layer consisting of skin epidermis and dermis, the epidermis layer of both groups were arranged on top of each other in a way that the multiple layers of flat epithelial cells arranged on top of each other were minimal (Figure 14,15).

The basal cells of the epidermis could be clearly recognized by the stratum basal and the densely stained stratum granule. There was no difference between the two groups in the epidermis layer. Corneum layer consisting of keratinized cells can be shown very well in two groups (figure 16).

It was shown that the corneum layer on the surface did not cause a difference as a result of the stitching process. The papillae of the connective tissue between the epidermis and the dermis were examined as indented. It was observed in both groups that the integrity of the loose connective tissue in the papillary layer, which is a layer of dermis, was not just underneath the

Fig.14.A.B. Changes of the suture removal device in the epidermis and hair follicle.

Fig.15.A.B. Stratum corneum and gland changes in classical methods.

Fig.16.A.B. Changes in the stratum corneum layer.

epidermis. In terms of epidermal structures with hair follicles, fat and sweat glands, the integrity of the tissues examined was not impaired (figure 17).

There was no capillary damage or bleeding in both groups.

Discussion

One of the most important goals of surgery is to combine the integrity and health of a deteriorated tissue with the lowest material loss and to restore its continuity and functionality [4]. It has been reported that there are disadvantages such as the formation of ischemia in the tissues and the length of the application period due to the tight application of the stitches [5]. Suture technique and suture as well as sewing materials are thought to be important. For example, Suzuki and his friends have developed a technique that can be sutured hard cervix uteri cerclage suture in patients with sutures can be taken more easily, this technique has called the name McDonald's procedure [6]. When taking the stitch through the conventional method, a lancet or scissors are usually required with a penset. Two tools and both hands need to be used for suture removal. During this process, all these materials come together, such as the use of hands together sometimes create problems such as time loss and complications such as skin injury, infection can cause complications. Studies are being done to prevent such problems [7]. When we evaluate the results of this study which investigated the effect of a new design with knife pliers on the wound, we can conclude that we have reached the bottom results.

It can be possible to take the sewing with one hand and one tool by using the newly designed suture receiver tool [8]. The rats in the two groups were homogeneous. There was no statistically significant difference between the suture removal time of both groups. Although the difference is not detected, the time in the classical method is less than the time in the new device group. However, this difference in mean values showed that the duration of stitching of the last rat approached the classic suturing time in 33 seconds when the duration curve of the new device was examined. This shows that the time to sew and get stitched becomes shorter during the operation. Considering that the classical stitching method has been applied for more than a century, it has been seen that this period is approached with the new device in a very short time and this situation is thought to be encouraging to use the new tool. We believe that with the increase of the usage of the new device, its speed will increase proportionally. Man and his friends in their study as a result of a new sutur-taking technique both the suture and sutur when taking the suture in the removal of pain in the technique developed by their own technique to compare the difference between the classic technique and sutures, the patient's pain, and the pathological deformities of the pain were compared. They did not find a difference between the classical method and the technique they applied [9]. In our study, suture time was comparable, but the pain scale could not be evaluated because it was an experimental study.

Regardless of the sewing material and technique, it is revealed in the investigations carried out by many researchers that it will minimize the various inflammatory events due to foreign body reaction with tissue adhesive. In addition, the material of the suture material against the wound lips as well as to ensure the integrity of the tissue thickness, frequency and time required to be taken in the tension, due to the capillary properties can lead to wound contamination and related complications such as many cases are significantly affected [5],[10],[11]. In our study, it

Fig.17.A.B. The effects of classical method on stratum corneum and sebaceous glands.

was found that trauma and tissue trauma were similar in both techniques and the new instrument did not cause tissue damage. Both the macroscopic and microscopic damage were similar in the tissue. Gurusamy and his friends in a study of the continuous suture technique with absorbable sutures after the operation can be better results in cosmetic terms, but the cosmetic situation may have changed from patient to patient stressed. In some cases, it is emphasized that individual sutures may be suitable and the timing and technique of sutures can be important [12]. In our study, we can say that the new instrument does not cause any different tissue damage than the classical method and this will not cause a negative result in cosmetic terms. Suzuki and his friends emphasized that some suture purchases were difficult even in their techniques [6]. With our technique and tool, suture intake was not a problem, and suture intake times decreased in each suture, suggesting that the experience was gained rapidly.

Result

This is the first experimental study comparing the use of a new surgical instrument with a conventional instrument. In our study, it was possible to compare hundreds of years of traditional methods and tools with a new instrument. Again, this study can be evaluated as a pioneering study that reports that there are many devices waiting to be invented in General Surgery. From this point of view, it is important to guide the similar studies. With this tool, it was aimed to gain both time and performance, and in part, these goals were achieved. Moreover, using the new instrument, it became easier to get difficult sutures. Again in our study, we observed that the time to take the suture with the new instrument approached the classical technique and this acceleration encouraged us to put the tool into practice.

References

1. Secord T, Shelton M. Suture removal device. <http://www.google.com/patents/WO2007134214A2?cl=en> (21.07.2014)
2. Straus AE. Suture Cutter. <http://patentscope.wipo.int/search/en/detail.jsf?docId=US36601148&recNum=1&office=&queryString=FP%3A%28US3659343+%2920prevFilter=&sortOption=Pub+Date+Desc&maxRec=1> (21.07.2014)
3. Chiu KW, Qiu H. Apparatus for punch biopsy. <http://www.google.com/patents/US20080039740> (21.07.2014)
4. Dart, A.J. and C.M. Dart, Suture Material: Conventional and Stimuli Responsive, in *Comprehensive Biomaterials*, P. Ducheyne, Editor 2011, Elsevier.574-587.
5. Thomazini-Santos A, Barraviera SRCS, Mendes-Giannini MJS and Barraviera B. Surgical adhesives, *J Venom Anim Toxins*, 2001;7, 2
6. Suzuki S. Cases of difficult suture removal following the McDonald procedure. doi:10.3109/14767058.2013.852179
7. Gurusamy KS, Toon CD, Allen VB, et al. Continuous versus interrupted skin sutures for non-obstetric surgery. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD010365.pub2

8. Boylu Ş, Soyder A, Bozdağ AD. Atraumatic sharp penset. 6. Surgical Research Congress. Poster presentation 8-10 December 2011, Ankara
9. Man SW, Yip SF, Chang YP. Bundled sutures and patient comfort during suture removal. *Hong Kong Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery* 2001;5(2):109-112
10. Masini, B.D., et al., Bacterial adherence to suture materials. *Journal of surgical education*, 2011. 68(2):101-4.
11. Scardino MS, Swaim SF, Morse SB, Sartin EA, Wright JC and Hoffman CE. Evaluation of fibrin sealants in cutaneous wound closure. *J Biomed Mater Res*, 1999;48,315-321
12. Gurusamy KS, Toon CD, Allen VB, et al. Continuous versus interrupted skin sutures for non-obstetric surgery. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD010365.pub2